

"RECENT UK PROGRESS IN THE APPLICATION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS"

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Ladies and gentlemen,

There remain only a few minutes of this Conference in which to give you a cross-section of the UK effort with advanced composites - mainly carbon-based of course.

Before doing so can I say something about the primary fibre producers.

Our three licencees report, against the general industrial trend, that there is a brisk demand for their products, production is rising and there is a steady stream of interesting enquiries from at home and abroad.

Turning to applications, we give pride of place to the aerospace industry. In the UK at least, it has the reputation of being low in volume, rich in problems and high in prestige.

Fig. 1 shows an experimental helicopter blade in CFRP. There is no doubt that composite blades are an increasingly important area of penetration. There are two possible advantages in using them. First of all the newer, more efficient blades with complex twist and curvature are more difficult to make in metal.

Second, the excellent fatigue life of CFRP; which is expected to produce significant increases in blade life, perhaps double the present limits.

We are always preaching that different materials require different designs, in other words each material should be handled sympathetically according to its particular attributes.

This helicopter blade is a good example.

So let us look at the blade interior, in Fig. 2, and see the simplification in design which follows a change of material.

On the right-hand side we have the original spar, made from thick stainless steel sheet.

Closing off the rear edge of the main spar involves forming two inward joggles, then rivetting them together to form a flange. The front of the trailing edge moulding must therefore be furnished with a reinforced cut-out in order to accommodate that flange. . . . All this because the stainless steel is too stiff and too strong to wrap!

On the other hand the soft, uncured sheets of carbon fibre pre-preg are easily wrapped. So that we have, for the CFRP spar on the left-hand side, first a layer wherein the fibre direction runs along the blade axis to take care of the bending moments, then successive layers laid diagonally across the blade, criss-cross fashion, in order to take care of the torsional loads.

The total weight saving amounts to about 40%.

In Fig. 3 we have an experimental Hawker Harrier wing-tip. This is typical of various components in CFRP - some larger and some smaller - which the British aircraft companies (BAC, HSA and Westland) are now designing and moulding with increased confidence.

The next slide, Fig. 4, shows an important potential money-spinner, more especially for large civil aircraft, i.e. floor panels.

This development was pioneered by Mr. Armstrong of the BOAC workshops, the man in the picture. The dark panel in the foreground was made by BCME (Bristol Composite Materials Engineering) Ltd to his requirements.

Such panels are of sandwich construction comprising crossed carbon fibre skins over a Nomex honeycomb core. They have shown themselves particularly resistant to indentation buckling and fatigue, both in laboratory tests and after extensive field trials. In fact they seem unharmed after 15,000 high-duty flying hours as against an average of perhaps 3000 hours of normal duty for the original metal-skinned panels.

What is meant by "high-duty"?

Well if one takes a panel designed for light loads, such as underseat passenger flooring, and deliberately places it in the gangway where the heaviest traffic flows. . . .

Yes, I see you have guessed correctly. The test panel was situated opposite the lower deck bar, at the foot of the staircase leading to the upper deck bar. . . .

Before leaving the aircraft field we should mention two applications concerned with aerodynamics. The first of these is the production of wind-tunnel models. Such models can be quite large (the delta-shaped model in Fig. 5 is well over a metre base and height) and they are very expensive when machined from thick steel plate.

Careful and accurate machining is needed to hollow out the steel and allow room for the hundreds of probe leads which give a pressure-plot of the surface.

The carbon-fibre models are moulded in two matching halves, with the hollow space for the leads already built into the design.

Apart from considerable cost and weight savings, the interesting technical point concerns the stiffness of the model itself. Although the absolute modulus of Type I CFRP is slightly lower than for steel, the CFRP model is as stiff as the metal one. The reduction in stiffness caused by boring hundreds of holes, is less for the fibre-reinforced skin than for metal, particularly in torsional loading.

Another neat application for CFRP is for the roll, pitch and yaw vanes of free-flight models. A typical assembly of vanes and pitot-tube is shown in Fig. 6. The requirements are that the cross-section must be very thin, with a low mass to give a quick response. At the same time the vanes must be accurately shaped, must retain this shape under air loadings and not be subject to breakage or warping due to accidental damage.

In other words, the aerodynamicist would like infinite strength and stiffness with zero density! Many materials have been tried, but so far CFRP seems nearest to specification.

Free-flight models often land heavily. In this case, the vanes were recovered intact from a depth of almost a metre after the model nosedived into a ploughed field at 80 m/sec near the Bedford establishment.

We now leave aircraft and consider the possibilities for reinforced plastics in another form of transportation, namely Hovercraft construction. Fig. 7 shows a typical, present generation Hovercraft of the rigid sidewall type, which make excellent ferries. The designer has made extensive use of sandwich construction, with CFRP skins and foamed plastics core. The earlier practice of making them

of rivetted light alloy - like an aircraft in fact - led to too many corrosion problems.

Future designs will be much larger. Fig. 8 shows a model of such a machine undergoing tests in a water-tank, and the question arises as to whether GRP skins will be sufficiently stiff or whether hybrid materials should be considered.

Of course GRP could be used alone - but in thicker sections - and the point comes when the increase in weight calls for some sacrifice in performance or pay-load. Experiments to decide the optimum construction are now in progress.

Having introduced the subject of hybrids, and while the academics argue as to the theory of fibre loading within them, can I say how simple it is in practice to upgrade traditional materials like timber or GRP and improve their performance.

Here is an example from the field of civil engineering. A large number of the GRP units, shown being moulded in Fig. 9, are used in the construction of box girder road bridges. The units must be light enough to be man-handled easily on site, yet strong and rigid to withstand, without distortion, the weight of wet concrete which is poured over them.

Studies at RAE, Surrey University, and elsewhere have shown that, in a folded plate design, complicated reinforcement of the flat faces is not necessary. Rather, at the ridges and valleys, a unidirectional stiffening, conveniently done with carbon fibre, is sufficient to delay buckling to the point where both plate stiffness and failing load are increased. Fig. 10 shows such stiffened panels being installed in the bed of the roadway prior to casting.

We feel that there must be many more instances where traditional wood and plywood shuttering can be improved as well as GRP. Indeed, the supplier of moulds for low-pressure lay-up work with reinforced plastics, should also ask himself whether a small proportion of carbon fibre can help to improve his product.

Another application where hybrids long ago proved their worth is in the construction of racing cars. Nowadays most of the body-shells comprise a carbon/glass hybrid. The illustration, Fig. 11, shows the GT40 Ford, winner of the 1968 and 1969 Le Mans 24-hour classic.

It proved possible to cut 60 lbs of deadweight off the body, to improve its fatigue life and to reduce the terrible drumming noises of the original shell, using only 10 lbs of carbon fibre.

Incidentally, it gives the author great pleasure to introduce in this photograph his colleagues and coinventors of the RAE carbon fibre, Bill Watt, OBE, right and Bill Johnson, centre.

Other applications are in the sport of rowing. Every British school-boy knows that Cambridge won the Boat Race and that their oars were upgraded with carbon fibre. Looking ahead, there is the challenge of the racing scull itself. The illustration of Fig. 12 shows a prototype single sculler but one has only to think of pairs, fours and eights to realize the potential market.

Needless to say, the object of this exercise is not to make a glass-fibre "tub" for training purposes but to crack the monopoly of hand-built wooden craft in serious national and international competition.

To give some idea of comparative weights, the entire hybrid hull, over 7 metres long, in Fig. 12 weighs 25 lbs but the metal-work shown in the cockpit of Fig. 13 weighs another 12 lbs. Surely this is also crying out for a re-design?

My last example, Fig. 14, a small but important example of upgraded wood, was chosen with some thought for the occasion. Here in Geneva, home of the Red Cross, with Mont Blanc and the Alps, if not quite looming above us, at least plainly visible on a clear day, I had to mention our work with the ice-axe on behalf of the International Committee for Safety in Mountaineering.

Although the ice-axe is a near perfect instrument in wood and tempered steel, there are unfortunate instances where the shaft has become embrittled and broken clean across. We have produced a simple, lightweight sheathing of carbon/glass hybrid, which substantially improves the stiffness and flexural strength of the axe, and, in the event of timber failure is sufficient also to take the climber's weight in direct tension.

Summarizing this brief report, the applications divide themselves naturally into two categories. For the first, maximum efficiency in performance is the requirement and expense is a secondary consideration. This class is typical of the aerospace industry and components are black, i.e. are 100% CFRP. In contrast, there are many other applications in the technical and sporting goods fields, where the cost and the performance are finely balanced, multi-coloured hybrids are common, and the question must be asked - "How much carbon fibre can we afford to upgrade the traditional material?"

Chairman's concluding remarks

I now put on my Chairman's hat for a few seconds to draw this Conference to a close. We thank the audience for being so attentive, patient and good-humoured throughout.

We thank the various speakers for giving such clear and detailed accounts of their work; and the organizers for bringing it all together.

Having listened to this morning's contributors, one cannot fail to be encouraged by the resource and ingenuity of the human mind; and the manner in which it first invents new materials and then finds uses for them - or as the cynics would say - vice versa!

Surely when we meet again there will be fresh wonders to report.

Goodbye, and a safe journey to you all!

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 7

Figure 6

Figure 8

GRP Shuttering Used In Box Girder Bridge

Figure 9

Figure 10

Figure 11

Figure 12